
Effects of Different Sowing Media on Germination and Early Growth of *Terminalia ivorensis* (A. Chev.)

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Abstract

Terminalia ivorensis is a tree species found in lowland rainforest zone in Nigeria but is predominantly a tree of seasonal forest zones. However, poor germination and inadequate silvicultural information are important factors militating against its regeneration. Therefore, this study is aimed at determining the effects of different sowing media on germination and early growth of *Terminalia ivorensis* with a view of knowing the best sowing media for raising *Terminalia ivorensis* at both germination and nursery stage. The experiment was arranged in a completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replicates. Viable seeds were sown into germination sieving baskets filled with four sowing media (Topsoil, sawdust, clay soil and river sand). Fifty seeds were sown into each germination sieving baskets. Data were collected on germination percentage and early growth parameters involving seedling height, collar diameter and leaf production. Analysis of variance was used to analyze the data collected. Means separation were carried out using the Least Significant Difference (LSD). The result revealed that germination percentage was significant at 5% level of probability. The highest germination percentage was recorded for treatment B (Sawdust) which had $4.80 \pm 30\%$ while treatments A (Topsoil) and D (River sand) had $4.60 \pm 28.5\%$ and $4.30 \pm 26\%$ respectively. The least was treatment C (Clay soil) which had $4.20 \pm 25.5\%$. There was significant difference at 5% level of probability in seedling height and collar diameter, but there was no significant difference in germination percentage and leaf production of *Terminalia ivorensis*. The highest mean height was recorded in treatment A (Topsoil) which has 14.64 ± 0.24 . Treatments B (Sawdust), C (Clay soil), D (River sand) had 13.33 ± 0.35 , 12.50 ± 0.60 and 12.35 ± 0.59 respectively.

The result showed that the highest diameter growth was recorded for treatment A (Topsoil) which has 2.49 ± 0.12 . Treatments B (Sawdust), D (River sand) and C (Clay soil) had 2.41 ± 0.05 , 1.96 ± 0.01 and 1.84 ± 0.01 respectively. Leaf production in *Terminalia ivorensis* was not significant between the treatments. The study has shown that the germination percentage of *Terminalia ivorensis* improved significantly with sowing media especially sawdust and topsoil. The use of sawdust and topsoil as sowing media for small and large scale propagation of the species is recommended.

Keywords: Seeds, Germination, Media, *Terminalia ivorensis*, Growth.

Received: 20/08/18

Accepted: 19/11/18

Introduction

Terminalia ivorensis is a tree species found in lowland rainforest zone in Nigeria but is predominantly a tree of seasonal forest zones. The species is one of the most important of some 200 species belonging to the genus *Terminalia*. Germination is the resumption of active embryo growth after a dormant period. The seed must be viable (the embryo must be alive and capable of germination). Low seed germination (vigor) is a function of the age and storage conditions of the planted seed as well as the health and maturity of the plant from which the seed was harvested. Internal conditions of the seed must be favorable for germination, that is, any physical, chemical, or physiological barriers to germination must have disappeared or must have been removed. The seed must be subjected to appropriate environmental conditions, including water (moisture), proper temperature, oxygen, and for some species, light. Forest-tree seeds have different germination rates and optimal temperatures.

Moisture is one essential condition for seed germination, and poor germination is very costly to growers. There is, nevertheless, little experimental evidence concerning the effects of different percentages of available moisture (Anber, 2010) on germination; more study of the subject is essential. Since most forest-tree seeds are planted at shallow depths, there may be rapid fluctuations of soil moisture around the seed, especially during the warmer months. This condition is common both to the irrigated soils of the west and to the soils of humid areas. Though several reports have been published concerning the effect of soil moisture upon germination, in no case has there been

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ISSN: 1597 - 9928 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

accurate measurement of the available soil moisture. Avery (2002) indicates that seed germination varies with the species of plant concerned as well as with the percentage of soil moisture. According to Dickens (2011), several species of forest-tree seeds respond differently to various amounts of supplementary water in addition to natural rainfall. Ibrahim (2004), studying the germination of New Zealand spinach, found it to be variable; but the germination was increased when the seeds were dried at intervals during the tests. McCork (2004) studied the combined effects of soil moisture and fertilizer placement on the germination of cabbage, snap beans, and pea seeds. In some treatments there were indications that low soil moisture and method of fertilizer application reduced germination. McDonald (2003) has studied the effect of soil moisture, temperature, and varieties of wheat upon germination. Germination was affected by these three factors. As Okunomo (2010) has shown, the seeds of several plant species will absorb water from solutions much higher in atmospheric pressure than 16 atmospheres (Takayama, 2005) which is approximately the pressure of the permanent wilting percentage (Anber, 2010). Xanthium seed proved able to extract water from a solution whose concentration was 1,000 atmospheres. Therefore, the study is aimed at determining the effects of different sowing media on germination and early growth of *Terminalia ivorensis* with a view of knowing the best sowing media for raising *Terminalia ivorensis* at both germination and nursery stage.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

The experiment was carried out in Nursery C of the Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan. The College is situated at Jericho Hill, Ibadan North West Local Government Area of Oyo State. The area lies between Latitude 7°26'N and Longitude 3°54'E. The annual rainfall ranges from 1400mm - 1500mm and average relative humidity of about 65%, the average temperature is 31.8°C.

Experimental Design and Treatment Procedure

The design used in this experiment was a Completely Randomized Design (CRD). The study involved the use of four (4) sowing media with three (3) replicates. The treatments were topsoil, sawdust, clay soil and river sand. Fifty (50) seeds were raised each for the different sowing media and a total of 200 seeds were used for the study. The seeds were broadcast in sieving baskets containing the different sowing media and kept in a humidified environment. The sieving baskets were watered daily. At the end of the germination experiment, 12 seedlings were randomly selected per sowing media,

and transplanted into polythene pots. Each polythene pot was regarded as individual replicate.

Experimental Layout

T _A	T _B	T _C	T _D
T _B	T _C	T _D	T _A
T _C	T _D	T _A	T _B

Where;

- T_A= Top soil
- T_B = Sawdust
- T_C = Clay soil
- T_D = River sand

Assessment of Growth Parameters

Daily observations were made to determine the effects of the four sowing media on the germination of seeds of *Terminalia ivorensis*. Germination recordings were discontinued and considered to have been completed when no additional germination took place in five weeks. Data were also collected on early seedling growth parameters: seedling height (cm), collar diameter (mm), number of leaves produced weekly. The growth parameters were measured for 16 weeks. The height of seedling in each pot was measured using a graduated meter rule. The Vernier caliper was used to measure the collar diameter of seedling in each pot. The production of new leaves was recorded by visual counting number of leaves produced weekly.

Data Analysis

Data collected on germination and early seedling growth were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) in a Completely Randomized Design. Percentage seed germination was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ germination} = \frac{x}{y} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where;

- x = number of seeds germinated
- y = number of seeds sown

Results and Discussion

Seed Germination

The result on effect of four (4) different sowing media on the germination of *Terminalia ivorensis* is shown in Table 1. The result shows that the highest mean germination percentage was recorded for treatment B (Sawdust) which had 4.80±30%. Treatment A (Topsoil) and D (River sand) had 4.60±28.5% and 4.30±26% respectively. The least was treatment C (Clay soil) which had 4.20±25.5%.

Table 1: Mean germination percentage of *Terminalia ivorensis* using different sowing media

Treatment	Mean S.E	± 95% confidence interval for mean		Minimum	Maximum
		Lower bound	Upper bound		
A (Topsoil)	4.60±0.21	2.88	4.24	3.00	4.00
B (Sawdust)	4.80±0.23	3.02	4.48	3.25	4.25
C (Clay Soil)	4.20±0.06	2.99	3.39	3.00	3.25
D (River Sand)	4.30±0.27	2.39	4.11	2.75	4.00

Where; S.E = Standard error

Early Seedling Growth

Seedling Height (cm)

The result on early seedling growth of *Terminalia ivorensis* using four (4) different sowing media is shown in Table 2. The result therefore shows that the highest mean height was recorded in treatment A (Topsoil) which has 14.64±0.24 followed by Treatment B (Sawdust), C (Clay soil), and D (River sand) had 13.33±0.35, 12.50±0.60 and 12.35±0.59 respectively. The mean seedling height of the species with the four sowing media were statistically significant at 5% level of significance with a value of 0.006 as shown in Table 3.

Table 2: Mean weekly seedling height of *Terminalia ivorensis* using different sowing media

Treatment	Mean ± S.E	95% confidence interval for mean		Minimum	Maximum
		Lower bound	Upper bound		
A (Topsoil)	14.64±0.24 ^{ab}	14.09	15.17	13.15	15.41
B (Sawdust)	13.33±0.35 ^c	12.53	14.13	12.15	15.30
C (Clay Soil)	12.50±0.60 ^a	11.14	13.85	9.87	15.59
D (River Sand)	12.35±0.59 ^b	11.02	13.68	9.92	15.22

Mean with same superscripts along the column are not significantly different from one another at $p < 0.05$ level of significance using least significant difference (LSD).

Table 3: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for seedling height

	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Treatments	32.872	3	10.957	4.936	0.006
Within Treatments	79.915	36	2.220		
Total	112.787	39			

Collar Diameter (mm)

The result on diameter growth of *Terminalia ivorensis* using four different sowing media is shown in Table 4. The result shows that the highest diameter growth was recorded for treatment A (Topsoil) has a value of 2.49 ± 0.12 . Treatment B (Sawdust), D (River sand) and C (Clay soil) had 2.41 ± 0.05 , 1.96 ± 0.08 and 1.84 ± 0.01 respectively. The mean collar diameter of the species with the four sowing media were highly significant at 5% level of significance with a value of 0.000 as presented in Table 5.

Table 4: Mean weekly diameter of *Terminalia ivorensis* using different sowing media

Treatment	Mean ± S.E	95% confidence interval for mean		Minimum	Maximum
		Lower bound	Upper bound		
A (Topsoil)	2.49±0.12 ^{ab}	2.23	2.76	2.03	3.08
B (Sawdust)	2.41±0.05 ^{ac}	1.77	2.15	1.61	2.44
C (Clay Soil)	1.84±0.01 ^{cd}	2.29	2.53	2.19	2.71
D (River Sand)	1.96±0.08 ^{bd}	1.62	2.05	1.56	2.59

Mean with same superscripts along the column are not significantly different from one another at $p < 0.05$ level of significance using LSD.

Table 5: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for diameter

	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Treatments	3.161	3	1.054	12.864	0.000
Within Treatments	2.948	36	0.082		
Total	6.109	39			

Leaf production

The mean weekly result on leaf production of *Terminalia ivorensis* using four (4) different sowing media is shown in Table 6. The result shows that the highest production of leaves was recorded for treatment A (Topsoil) which has 12.47 ± 0.41 and treatment D (River sand) had 12.35 ± 0.65 . Treatment B (Sawdust) had 11.91 ± 0.60 and the least was treatment C (Clay soil) which had 1.43 ± 0.54 . The mean seedling leaf production of the species with the four sowing media were not statistically significant at 5% level of significance with a value of 0.544 as revealed in Table 7.

Table 6: Mean monthly leaf production of *Terminalia ivorensis* using different sowing media

Treatment	Mean \pm S.E	95% confidence interval for mean		Minimum	Maximum
		Lower bound	Upper bound		
A (Topsoil)	12.47 ± 0.41	11.42	13.28	10.60	14.70
B (Sawdust)	11.91 ± 0.60	10.56	13.26	8.00	14.20
C (Clay Soil)	11.43 ± 0.54	10.22	12.64	9.60	14.90
D (River Sand)	12.35 ± 0.65	10.99	13.94	9.40	15.90

Table 7: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for leaf production

	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Treatments	6.700	3	2.233	0.724	0.544
Within Treatments	111.056	36	3.085		
Total	117.756	39			

Conclusion

The study has shown that the germination percentage of *Terminalia ivorensis* improved significantly with sowing media especially sawdust and topsoil. This will play an important role in ensuring uniform and maximum germination of the species in the nursery and any subsequent afforestation or re-vegetation programme using the species stand successful. This result will be most useful to forest nursery practitioners and other scientists working for sustainable management of this species.

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